

Comparative Neutronic Analysis of Uranium-based Fuel Matrices on the BANDI-60 SMR for Maritime Applications

Maia O.G. Wirgenes^{1,*}

¹University of Oslo, Institute of Physics, Sem Sælands vei 24, Oslo, Norway

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803634

ABSTRACT

Nuclear propulsion is a potential solution for decarbonizing the shipping industry by 2050. To be viable, it must demonstrate economic competitiveness, high safety standards, and responsible spent-fuel management. This study investigates fuel utilization and performance optimization in a Small Modular Reactor (SMR), where the South Korean BANDI-60 functions as a baseline model. A fuel- and enrichment-variation analysis is conducted through depletion simulations with the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC. 13 fuel matrix configurations are examined, evaluating their effects on cycle length, burnup, and radionuclide inventory evolution. The results show that fuel matrix continuity and the fuel-to-moderator ratio strongly influence fuel utilization and overall reactor performance. These parameters drive observable differences in energy production potential and actinide buildup across the models. The study highlights the importance of fuel microstructure and composition in achieving efficient, sustainable reactor operation for future marine nuclear propulsion systems.

Keywords: Fuel Utilization, Small Modular Reactors, Maritime Reactor Technology, Neutronics Simulations, OpenMC

1. INTRODUCTION

International and national policies have intensified efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in hard-to-abate sectors such as shipping. Owing to the industry's high energy demand, diverse vessel types, and reliance on long-distance operations, it is dependent on reliable and flexible propulsion systems. Recognizing that the sector's current propulsion system solution is reliable for roughly 90% of its total emissions [1, 2], Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) have emerged as a promising decarbonization option. Designed for factory fabrication, lower capital cost, and enhanced safety, SMRs also offer improved fuel utilization, proliferation resistance, and modular scalability. Their ability to support multi-unit configurations enables operational redundancy and resilience, making them particularly suited for remote and mobile applications such as marine propulsion [3, 4].

Nuclear propulsion has a long history, emerging only a decade after the first developments in nuclear technology, driven by naval innovation during and after World War II. The adoption of Pressurized Water Reactor technology by the US Navy, first demonstrated in the USS Nautilus, established the earliest example of SMRs, which enabled increases in endurance, speeds, and extended core lifetimes of submarines. More than 700 naval reactors have since operated at sea, making both PWR-based marine propulsion and the SMR concept well-established. Many new SMR designs have novel design features with little operational history, while PWRs have over 70 years of proven use in both naval and stationary reactors. This is believed to result in regulatory and licensing advantages for marine applications. However, SMRs based on PWR-designs face limitations in efficiency and burnup [3, 4, 5]. To address these, this study compares three fuel matrices at five enrichment levels to explore potential improvements in burnup and fuel-utilization. The South Korean PWR-based BANDI-60 is chosen as the base model.

*m.o.g.wirgenes@fys.uio.no

2. COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF UO_2 , U_3Si_2 , AND TRISO FUEL CONCEPTS

SMR designs aim for flatter power densities to achieve more uniform burnup and longer, more cost-effective fuel cycles. Applied fuel types, enrichment levels, and heavy-metal densities play a central role by setting fissile inventory, shaping reactivity, and energy production. Ultimately, the three fuel parameters govern the neutronic behavior and fuel-cycle performance. Variations in these form the basis for comparing three fuel types: conventional UO_2 , metallic U_3Si_2 , and TRISO-based UO_2 .

2.1. Continuous- and Non-Continuous Fuel Matrices

UO_2 is the standard nuclear fuel, backed by decades of operational experience and well-understood performance. U_3Si_2 , developed for research reactors in the 1980s, has since gained attention for its high uranium density, superior thermal conductivity, and stable swelling behavior, making it an attractive accident-tolerant option for light-water reactors [6, 7]. Both fuels are used as solid pellets that occupy the fuel-rod volume. TRISO fuels, originating from the 1960s Dragon Project, consist of uranium-based kernels encapsulated in multiple carbon and ceramic layers, offering exceptional retention of fission products and high tolerance to temperature and irradiation. Currently considered the most robust form of nuclear fuel, TRISO particles with a diameter of about 1 mm are embedded in a graphite or SiC matrix rather than forming "continuous" solid pellets [8, 9]. Their discrete structure introduces a packing fraction (PF), which in a SiC matrix has a practical upper limit of $\sim 40\%$ [10].

3. REACTOR PHYSICS FUNDAMENTALS

The energy produced in a reactor originates from the fission of fissile nuclei such as ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu . About 200 MeV and 2–3 fast neutrons are released per fission event. A self-sustaining chain reaction, labeled criticality, occurs when each succeeding generation produces the same number of neutrons as the previous generation. Neutrons span thermal to fast energies, where fission of fissile nuclei strongly favors thermal energies. Reactivity is a measure of a system's deviation from criticality, where criticality corresponds to steady-state operation. The reactivity of a reactor system depends on the balance between the production, absorption, and leakage of neutrons.

3.1. Reaction Rates & the Effective Multiplication Factor

Neutron reaction rates are governed by energy-dependent microscopic cross sections $\sigma(E)$ and neutron flux $\phi(E)$, where the reaction rate for a specific reaction i is

$$R_i = \int \phi(E)\sigma_i(E)dE. \quad (1)$$

While fissile isotopes favor thermal fission, fertile isotopes (^{238}U and ^{240}Pu) absorb in the epithermal region. Moderator materials (water, graphite) shape the neutron spectrum by slowing neutrons. In this way, the probability for fission reactions is enhanced. The effective multiplication factor k_{eff} denotes the system's reactivity. Its physical basis can be expressed as the product of five factors, representing processes that may add or remove neutrons from the system

$$k_{\text{eff}} = \eta f \varepsilon p P_{\text{NL}}, \quad (2)$$

linking the roles of neutron reproduction (η), utilization (f), fast fission (ε), resonance escape (p) and leakage (P_{NL}). Burnup-driven changes in fissile content, spectra, and absorber isotope presence govern the evolution of k_{eff} .

3.2. Spectrum Dependency on Moderation & Self-Shielding Effects, and Effects on Fuel Depletion

The presence of resonance absorbers (^{238}U and ^{240}Pu) creates *energy self-shielding* effects, while the spatial heterogeneity of isotopes produces *spatial self-shielding* effects. Both phenomena significantly alter neutron flux distributions, and the fuel-moderator geometry directly sets the neutron spectrum. Spatially continuous fuels are more uniformly moderated, whereas the discontinuous geometry of TRISO fuels alters the neutron spectrum and thus the evolution of k_{eff} . Hard spectra favor fertile-to-fissile conversion, while soft spectra enhance fission efficiency and burnup. These spectral differences lead to distinct trends in depletion and reactivity, which form a comparison basis for the three fuel matrices, under otherwise identical conditions, investigated in this paper.

4. METHODOLOGY

The parametric study evaluates 13 models of the BANDI-60 reactor core (Table I). Due to fuel-loading limitations set by the PF in the TRISO matrix, only the three highest enriched cases went critical.

Table I. Fuel matrix and enrichment combinations for BANDI-60 core analysis

Pellet-based UO_2	TRISO w/ UO_2	Pellet-based U_3Si_2
4.95%	–	4.95%
10%	–	10%
20%	20%	20%
30%	30%	30%
40%	40%	40%

Geometry, temperatures, and simulation settings are constant for all simulations. Each model is depleted until $k_{\text{eff}} = 1$ to compare cycle lengths, discharge burnup, and radionuclide inventories.

4.1. Model Verification & Implementation in OpenMC

A baseline BANDI-60 model (4.95 wt% UO_2) was constructed from available literature data and verified against published Beginning-of-Life (BOL) k_{eff} , cycle lengths and discharge burnup values [11, 12, 13]. After validation, the U_3Si_2 and TRISO models were implemented using the same geometric framework.

Figure 1. Illustration of a non-continuous (TRISO, left) and continuous (UO_2 , right) fuel matrix.

Specifications for material and geometry implementation in OpenMC [14] followed from published BANDI-60 design parameters [15, 11, 16], shown in Table II and Table III. Materials are defined via

atomic fractions with self-normalized density assignments and temperature-dependent properties. Thermal scattering data are applied through $S(\alpha, \beta)$ tables added to the water moderator and carbon layers in the TRISO fuel. The core consists of an 17×17 PWR Westinghouse assembly layout, arranged in an 8×8 assembly lattice, modeled with all control rods fully withdrawn (filled with helium).

Table II. Core geometry overview used in OpenMC

Item	Specification
Pin geometry	Cylindrical pins with concentric regions: fuel/Pyrex (0.4096 cm), He gap (0.4180 cm), and Zircaloy4 cladding (0.4750 cm).
Pin types	Fuel pins: UO_2 , U_3Si_2 , or TRISO (UO_2 kernel in SiC matrix). BA pins: Pyrex.
Assembly design	Westinghouse 17×17 layout; 24 BA pr. assembly
Reactivity management	Five Pyrex compositions (5–40 wt% B_2O_3) used to enable boron-free reactivity control
Core layout	8×8 lattice containing 52 assemblies

Table III. Material properties and thermal data applied in OpenMC

Material / Region	Specification
Moderator (H_2O)	0.654 g/cm ³ @ 600 K.
Fuel (UO_2)	10.76 g/cm ³ @ 900 K.
Fuel (U_3Si_2)	11.23 g/cm ³ @ 900 K.
TRISO components (g/cm ³)	Kernel 10.96; Buffer 1.05; iPyC 1.90; SiC 3.20; oPyC 1.87; SiC matrix 3.20 @ 600 K.
TRISO layers (mm)	Kernel 0.425; Buffer 0.475; iPyC 0.510; SiC 0.545; oPyC 0.580
Gap (He)	2.499×10^{-3} g/cm ³ @ 900 K.
Cladding (Zircaloy4)	6.45 g/cm ³ @ 600 K.

4.1.1. TRISO Fuel Implementation & Reactivity Management

TRISO layer dimensions are shown in Table III [10]. The PF was tuned to match the BOL k_{eff} of the baseline model. As criticality was only achievable for enrichments $\geq 20\%$, corresponding to a PF of 36.12%, this model served as the baseline for the TRISO matrix. Boron-free reactivity control is achieved using Pyrex burnable absorber rods. Five compositions (5–40 wt% B_2O_3) are generated from standard Pyrex glass formulations, producing five assembly variants that construct an optimized core pattern with a 10:1 fuel-to-BA pin ratio.

4.2. Simulation Settings & Depletion Scheme

Fluxes, spectra, heat generation, and normalization were obtained through designated tallies (Table IV). All models share identical simulation settings and use the same depletion chain, operator, and integrator (Table V). In total, 10.5×10^6 active particles were used in all simulations, depleting all models until $k_{\text{eff}} = 1$. For cases where the cycle lengths were underestimated, the simulations were extended using linear extrapolation of the slopes of $k_{\text{eff}}(t)$ (Figure 3). Radionuclide inventories for key isotopes were extracted from depletion output files and analyzed over the full cycle length.

Table IV. Tallies implemented for all simulations

Tally	Scores	Filters	Use
Mesh	Flux, heating-local	50 × 50 mesh	Flux distribution
Source	Fission, heating-local	All regions/energies	Normalization
Fission	Fission, kappa/nu-fission	All regions/energies	MeV per fission
Flux	Flux	Thermal-fast groups	Spectrum

Table V. Depletion setup overview

	Operator	Integrator
Name	deplete.CoupledOperator()	deplete.CECMIntegrator()
Type	Transport-coupled operator	Predictor-corrector semi-implicit
Key parameters	Unique geometry/material model	Variable time steps
	ENDF/B-VII.1 chain	Coupled operator
	Fission Q-value normalization	200 MW _{th} power

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

OpenMC's depletion calculations provide $k_{\text{eff}}(t)$, cycle length, discharge burnup, flux spectra, and radionuclide inventories for all 13 BANDI-60 models. The same work was repeated for higher enrichment levels, which confirmed that the same qualitative trends persist for the selected enrichment range.

5.1. Flux Spectra, Reactivity Evolution and Burnup

The reference spectra (Figure 2) confirm the proper implementation of all three fuel matrices. UO_2 and U_3Si_2 exhibit nearly identical spectra, with modest hardening for U_3Si_2 as a consequence of its higher uranium density. TRISO shows a relatively hardened spectrum, consistent with its microstructured geometry and additional scattering in the coating layers.

Figure 2. Normalized neutron flux spectra for the three base fuel matrices. The pr pin normalization (left) highlight differences in flux magnitude between fuel concepts, whereas spectra normalized to unit integral (right) highlight differences in spectral shape.

Continuous fuel matrices display smooth $k_{\text{eff}}(t)$ curves under lumped Pyrex control, with expected early suppression and gradual decline. U_3Si_2 reaches its inflection earlier due to slightly faster poison depletion in the harder spectrum. The behavior is also reflected in burnup, where U_3Si_2 slightly outperform UO_2 . The TRISO matrix $k_{\text{eff}}(t)$ curve differs markedly from these, showing a reduced initial suppression, broad mid-cycle plateau, and a delayed decline. This is consistent with reduced effectiveness of lumped absorbers in a hardened spectrum and a geometry where poisons are not co-located with fissile material. Reactivity is sustained primarily through actinide breeding rather than the burnable absorber

loading efficiency. TRISO achieves the highest burnup by a large margin, supported by strong ^{239}Pu production in the hardened spectrum, longer irradiation time, and higher fissile content (Figure 3).

Figure 3. k_{eff} evolution (left) and burnup curves (right) for the three base fuel matrices.

5.2. Radionuclide Inventories

The plutonium buildup curves directly reflect the spectral behavior of the three matrices (top row of Figure 4). For TRISO, an early increase of ^{239}Pu and a sustained transmutation is evident, while the continuous fuels exhibit standard saturation toward End-of-Life (EOL). U_3Si_2 accumulates slightly more across the considered Pu isotopes than UO_2 , due to the higher ^{238}U content. Higher actinides are dominated by ^{237}Np in all matrices but reach the highest levels in the TRISO matrix, a result reflecting the longer exposure time for this model. Fission-product inventories scale with total energy extraction, where TRISO again yields the highest concentrations. Short-lived fission products (e.g., ^{131}I) remain negligible at EOL for all matrices.

Figure 4. Isotopic inventory evolution for the three base matrices. Plutonium (top), higher actinides (middle), selected fission products (bottom)

6. CONCLUSIONS

The presented results highlight the affects of fuel microstructure and heavy-metal distribution on neutron spectra, reactivity behavior, and achievable cycle lengths. The U_3Si_2 matrix provides modest burnup gains over UO_2 as a consequence of higher uranium density while retaining a similar neutron spectrum. Due to their similar behavior, U_3Si_2 appears to be compatible with existing UO_2 -based designs and reactivity-control strategies, supporting its potential for increased burnup in maritime applications. The TRISO matrix achieves the highest discharge burnup, driven by its hardened neutron spectrum and associated transuranic buildup. However, its microstructured geometry reduces the effectiveness of lumped burnable absorbers, necessitating alternative reactivity control strategies, and precludes the near-direct implementation feasible for U_3Si_2 . In short, U_3Si_2 offer incremental performance improvement over UO_2 and operational familiarity, while TRISO presents significant endurance benefits at the cost of more complex reactivity management. Additionally, higher enrichments must be used, due to PF limitations. Both remain viable candidates for marine SMRs, where long cycle lengths, autonomy, and inherent safety are valued and necessary priorities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

A great thanks to my supervisors, Ole C. Reistad and Sunniva Siem, who have guided and supported me throughout this project, and the entire nuclear physics group at the University of Oslo. Many thanks for your constant support, encouragement, and the positive environment that has shaped my academic journey.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. S. E.-E. R. Bhattacharyya and F. Khalid. "Climate Action for the Shipping Industry: Some Perspectives on the Role of Nuclear Power in Maritime Decarbonization." *e-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, volume 4, p. 100616 (2023).

- [2] D. P. Team. "Energy Transition Outlook 2023: MARITIME FORECAST TO 2050." Technical report, Det Norske Veritas (2023).
- [3] S. H. et al. "Considerations on the Potential Use of Nuclear Small Modular Reactor (SMR) Technology for Merchant Marine Propulsion." *Ocean Engineering*, **volume 79**, pp. 101–130 (2014).
- [4] I. A. E. Agency. "Small Modular Reactors Catalogue 2024." Technical report, IAEA (2024). Supplement to: Small Modular Reactors: Advances in Developments 2024).
- [5] B. J. H. et al. "Identification of Nuclear Reactor Systems for International Commercial Marine Vessels: The Shipping Perspective." In *Proc. Int. Conf. Ships and Offshore Structures (ICSOS 2025)*. Gothenburg, Sweden (2025).
- [6] G. H. J.L. Snelgrove and R. B. J. Rest. "Advances in the Understanding of U3Si2-Al Dispersion Fuel Irradiation Behavior." Technical report, Argonne National Laboratory (1995). Proc. 4th Int. Group On Research Reactors Meetings, Gatlinburg, USA, pp.253–275.
- [7] J. R. M. R. Finlay, G. L. Hofman and J. L. Snelgrove. "Behaviour of Irradiated Uranium Silicide Fuel Revisited." Technical report, Argonne National Laboratory (2002). Presented at RERTR 2002, San Carlos de Bariloche, Argentina.
- [8] B. Wells and K. Geelhood. "TRISO Fuel: Properties and Failure Modes." Technical report, Pacific Northwest National Laboratories (2021). Prepared for the U.S. NRC, Contract DE-AC05-76RL01830.
- [9] U. D. of Nuclear Energy. "TRISO Particles: The Most Robust Nuclear Fuel on Earth." Online. URL <https://www.energy.gov/ne/articles/triso-particles-most-robust-nuclear-fuel-earth>. Accessed: Nov.21, 2025.
- [10] N. Brown. "High Volume Packing Fraction TRISO-based Fuel in Light Water Reactors." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 146**, p. 104151 (2022).
- [11] J. S. D. Kim, H.J. Shim. "Comparison of Core Design Parameters for BANDI-60 Using UO2 and U-Mo Fuels." Technical report, Seoul National University / KEPCO E&C (2022). Trans. Korean Nuclear Society Spring Meeting, Jeju, Korea, May 19-20, 2022.
- [12] J. S. D. Kim and H. Shim. "Comparison of BANDI-60 Core Designs using Pyrex Burnable Absorber and Annular Fuel Embedding Gadolinia Wire." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 195**, p. 110119 (2024).
- [13] D. Kim. "Boron-Free Small Modular Reactor Design by McCARD Burnup Calculation with T/H Feedback." Technical report, Seoul National university Monte Carlo Laboratory (2020). Trans. Korean Nuclear Society Autumn Meeting, 2020.
- [14] P. K. R. et. al. "OpenMC: A state-of-the-art Monte Carlo code for Research and Development." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 80**, pp. 90–97 (2015).
- [15] I. K. et. al. "Development of BANDI-60S for a Floating Nuclear Power Plant." Technical report, KEPCO E&C, New Technology Business Group (2019). Trans. Korean Nuclear Society Spring Meeting, Jeju, Korea, 2022.
- [16] I. A. E. Agency. *Advances in Small Modular Reactor Technology Developments*. IAEA, 2022 edition (2022).